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Belt conveyor System in Construction industry: A review

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ABSTRACT

Belt conveyor systems are widely used material handling systems in construction projects for transporting bulk materials efficiently. This study focused on the design criteria, components, advantages, factors affecting usage, and types of belt conveyors used in construction. The integrated system flow framework included stages such as material input, conveying process, output, and monitoring and control for effective operation. Different types of conveyors like flat, inclined, cleated, roller bed, and modular conveyors were studied based on their applications. The system helps in continuous transportation, reduces manual labour, improves safety, and increases productivity. It also ensures efficient handling of materials like sand, aggregates, and concrete. However, factors like maintenance requirements and initial cost may affect its performance. Overall, belt conveyor systems provide a systematic and efficient approach for material handling in construction projects.

Keywords: *Belt conveyor system, construction industry, material handling, design, safety, cost*

INTRODUCTION

Belt conveyor systems are one of the most commonly used material handling systems in construction projects. They are used to transport bulk materials such as concrete, cement, aggregates, debris, and excavated earth efficiently from one place to another.[1]

They were invented in 1892 by Thomas Robins for conveying coal, ores, and other

materials. These systems can move large quantities continuously over long distances at high speed, making them very useful in large projects like roads, bridges, and buildings.

A belt conveyor consists of an endless belt running over rollers or pulleys to carry materials smoothly and efficiently, reducing manual work and increasing productivity.

Fig. 1: Belt Conveyor in Construction work.

Figure 1 show a belt conveyor system used for transporting bulk materials like stones and aggregates. The conveyor belt moves over rollers and pulleys, carrying materials efficiently.[2] One image shows material discharge from an inclined conveyor, while the other highlights the belt structure and

arrangement, ensuring smooth, continuous material handling in construction work.

Components of Belt Conveyor System

The following table 1 showing the Components of Belt Conveyor System:

Table 1: Components of Belt Conveyor System [3].

No.	Components	Function	Image
1	Belt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main part of the conveyor that carries materials from one location to another.[4] 	
2	Motor [5]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supplies the mechanical power required to drive the conveyor system. 	

3	Gearbox	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduces speed and increases torque for smooth belt operation. 	
4	Pulley [6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used to drive, guide, & maintain tension in the belt. Types of Pulleys [7] : <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Drive pulley 2) Tail pulley 3) Snub pulley 4) Bend pulley 5) Take-up pulley 	
5	Idler Rollers [6]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support the loaded and unloaded belt and ensure smooth movement with minimum friction. Types of Idlers [7] : <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Carrying idlers 2) Return idlers 3) Impact idlers 4) Transition idlers 	<p>[8]</p>
6	Loading System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used for proper loading of materials onto the belt. Loading Devices: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Chute, 2) Transfer conveyor, 3) Vibratory feeder 	

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following are literature reviews on Always better control in construction projects:

Jakubovicova et. al. (2022) Investigated the performance and optimization of belt conveyor systems. Analysed factors such as friction, load distribution, and belt speed affecting system efficiency. Evaluated the impact of operational and environmental conditions. Found that optimization improved performance and reduced energy consumption. Concluded that advanced design and analysis techniques increased reliability and cost-effectiveness. Highlighted the importance of efficient conveyor systems in construction and material handling industries.[5]

Pati et al. (2020) Studied the design and analysis of a belt conveyor system to improve efficiency in material handling. Analysed parameters such as belt width, speed, tension, and power requirements. Evaluated system performance under different working conditions. Found that proper design reduced energy consumption and improved operational efficiency. Concluded that optimized conveyor design enhanced reliability and minimized maintenance issues. Highlighted the importance of selecting suitable materials and components for better durability in construction and industrial applications.[3]

Todkar et. al. (2018) Analysed the design methodology of belt conveyor systems used in industrial applications. Studied calculations related to load capacity, motor power, and belt tension. Examined components like rollers, pulleys, and belts for effective performance. Observed that accurate design ensured smooth material flow and reduced failures. Concluded that proper alignment and regular maintenance improved efficiency. Emphasized that systematic design was essential for achieving high productivity and reducing downtime.[6]

Majumdar et. al. (2018) Investigated the structural design and mechanical efficiency of belt conveyor systems through detailed engineering analysis. They utilized Finite Design criteria, Types and Application of Belt Conveyor in construction industry.

Element Method (FEM) software to simulate various loading conditions and evaluated the stresses on critical drive components. The study analyzed how the selection of high-torque motors and optimized idler spacing influenced both energy consumption and system durability. Found that precise engineering of belt tension significantly reduced mechanical wear and operational costs. Concluded that advanced simulation techniques provided a more reliable framework for designing material handling systems in harsh industrial environments. Highlighted the necessity of integrating robust structural supports to maintain high performance in large-scale construction applications.[7]

The following table 2 showing the design criteria of Belt Conveyor System:

Table 2: Design criteria of Belt Conveyor System [6] [9]

No.	Design Parameters	Formula/Basis of calculation
1	Belt Width	$B = \sqrt{\frac{Q}{3.6 k v \rho}}$ <p>Where, B = belt width (m) Q = conveyor capacity (t/h) k = capacity factor (depends on trough angle) v = belt speed (m/s) p = bulk density of material (t/m³)</p>
2	Belt Speed	$v = \frac{\pi DN}{60}$ <p>Where, v = belt speed (m/s) D = diameter of drive pulley (m) N = rotational speed of pulley (rpm)</p>
3	Cross-Section Area	$A = B^2 \times K$ <p>Where, A = Cross-Section Area B² = diameter of drive pulley (m) K = Cross-Section factor</p>
4	Driving Force	$Te = R + Rs + Rsp + Rsl$ <p>Where, R = Main Resistance Rs = Secondary Resistance</p>

		Rsp = Special Resistance Rsl = Slope Resistance
5	Power Required	$P = \frac{(T_1 - T_2) v}{1000}$ Where, P = power required at drive pulley (kW) T1 = tight side belt tension (N) T2 = slack side belt tension (N) V = belt speed (m/s)
6	Factor Of Safety [2]	$FOS = \frac{\text{Ultimate Strength}}{\text{Working Stress}}$

**TYPES OF BELT CONVEYOR USED
IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY**
Flat Belt Conveyor [10]

Used to transport materials like sand, gravel, and cement on flat surfaces with a simple structure, low cost, and smooth operation over short to medium distances

Inclined/Declined Conveyor

Used to move construction materials efficiently between different heights, carrying materials upward or downward

with proper design to prevent slipping and ensure safe transport.

Cleated Belt Conveyor

Provided with raised cleats on the belt surface to prevent material sliding, making

it suitable for transporting loose materials on steep inclines safely and efficiently.

Roller Bed Conveyor

Uses rollers to support the belt and reduce friction, allowing efficient transportation of

heavy materials like bricks, stones, and blocks over longer distances with less power.

Modular Belt Conveyor

Made of interlocking segments, it is durable and flexible, suitable for handling bulky,

irregular, or sharp materials, and allows easy maintenance by replacing damaged sections only.

APPLICATION OF BELT CONVEYOR IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

1. Tunneling and Underground Works: Used to transport excavated soil and debris from tunnels continuously, improving efficiency and reducing manual labor.
2. Road and Highway Construction: Used to move aggregates and asphalt materials over long distances, ensuring continuous supply and faster work.
3. Bridge Construction Projects: Used for transporting concrete and aggregates to difficult locations efficiently.
4. Concrete Batching Plants: Used to carry cement, sand, and aggregates to mixing units for continuous and accurate feeding.
5. Material Handling at Construction Sites: Used for general transport of

bulk materials, reducing manual work and increasing productivity.

6. Debris and Waste Removal: Used to remove construction waste efficiently, maintaining site cleanliness and safety.

INTEGRATED SYSTEM FLOW FRAMEWORK

The provided figure 2 shows an Integrated System Flow Framework for Belt Conveyor operation in construction. The diagram explains the movement of materials from the input stage to the final output, along with monitoring and feedback for better performance. It presents a clear flow of activities involved in material handling using a belt conveyor system.[11] The framework includes four main stages: Material Input, Conveying Process, Output, and Monitoring & Control. Each stage plays an important role in efficient material transportation.

Fig. 2: Integrated System Flow Framework of Belt Conveyor System.

1. **Material Input:** This stage involves loading materials such as sand, gravel, or concrete onto the conveyor belt. Proper loading is important to avoid spillage and ensure smooth operation.
2. **Conveying Process:** In this stage, materials are transported through the belt conveyor system. The speed, alignment, and condition of the belt affect efficiency and performance.[11]
3. **Output:** This stage includes the unloading of materials at the required location. Proper discharge helps in accurate placement and reduces material loss.
4. **Monitoring & Control:** This stage involves checking system performance, maintenance, and safety measures. It helps in avoiding breakdowns and improving system efficiency.

Overall, this framework shows how materials are efficiently handled using a belt conveyor system in construction projects. It helps in reducing manual work, saving time, lowering cost, and improving overall productivity.

Advantages of Belt Conveyor in Construction Industry

- Capable of transporting large quantities of materials efficiently over long distances. [1]

- Reduces manual labor, thereby saving time and lowering operational cost.[12]
- Provides continuous and automated operation, increasing overall productivity.
- Can handle materials of different sizes and types with ease.
- Suitable for use in tunnels, underground works, and various construction site applications.

Factor for use of belt conveyor system

- Suitable for transporting large quantities of materials efficiently over long distances.
- Improves safety by reducing manual handling through automated operation. [3]
- Requires low maintenance compared to other material handling systems.
- Reduces the risk of accidents and injuries at construction sites. [3]
- Requires less labor, thereby lowering overall operational costs. [12]

CONCLUSION

The following are conclusions based on the study of belt conveyor systems in construction projects:

1. Belt conveyor systems provide efficient and continuous transportation of bulk materials in construction projects.

2. They reduce manual labour and improve safety through automated material handling.
3. Proper design parameters and selection of components ensure smooth operation and better performance.
4. Different types of belt conveyors are suitable for various construction applications and site conditions.
5. The integrated system flow framework helps in systematic material movement and effective monitoring.
6. Overall, belt conveyor systems help in saving time, reducing cost, and increasing productivity in construction projects.

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